

FORMATOR®

High material efficiency in wood panels through smart precision equipment

Wood panels are produced in a large-scale process where wood chips are sprayed on a continuous conveyor belt and compressed into boards. This smart mat spraying system uses sensors for precision measurements to reduce the weight per unit area without loss in panel quality.

Highlights of innovative features

- The precision system automatically controls the homogenisation of weight in the panel. Excess material is removed by finetuned scalper rolls and returned immediately into the process.
- Perfectly formed panels with the desired optimal mechanical properties of the final product can be produced. Customer-specific offsets can be realised with highest precision. Advanced detection of risk potentials such as metals or glue lumps is also included.
- Raw material savings can attain 2% or 16 kg/m³, which correspond to about 9.9 million kg per year in a typical MDF production line.

The system allows for large material and energy savings resulting from reduced use of wood, less glue, reduced energy demand, less waste, and less logistics cost due to lower panel weight.

The system ensures optimal use of the raw material in the panel product by avoiding production wastes and hence reduce pressure on forest resources.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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